

Appendix B: target by target notes

In the following we report a summary of the main properties derived for each target. For each target we also show:

- Left: Optical image (SDSS u filter) with σ_{rms} \cdot [-3,3,6,12,24,48,96] contours of the LoTSS (145 MHz, green), and proprietary ones (1.5 GHz, white and 6 GHz, yellow).
- Middle: Radio map. Colours at 6 GHz with σ_{rms} \cdot [-3, 3, 6, 12, 24, 48, 96] contours at 1.5 GHz (white) and 145 MHz (green). The beams are shown at the bottom left of each, so that it is possible to appreciate the different resolutions. The black cross marks the optical position of the AGN.
- Right: SED. The points are the integrated flux densities extracted from the proprietary data and LoTSS (blue filled dots), those of TGSS, RACS and FIRST and VLASS (grey dots). When different epochs of VLASS are shown, they are plotted with xs in different shades of grey.

Fig. 1. 2MASXJ0220-07. The linear size is < 3.66 kpc. The SED is very flat at GHz frequencies, and the offset of RACS, FIRST and VLASS flux densities with respect to the computed slopes suggests strong variability. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is consistent with the IR deduced one within 3σ . The target exceeds the 3σ uncertainty around the Güdel–Benz relation. According to the spectral shape, and given the offset with respect to the Güdel–Benz relation, we conclude the radio emission is most likely due to an unresolved compact jet.

Fig. 2. WISEJ0537-02. The linear size is < 1.8 kpc. The SED is steep at GHz, within the uncertainties. No UFO detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is consistent with the IR deduced one within 2σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. According to the spectral shape, we conclude the radio emission is most likely due to an unresolved compact jet, however some contribution from SF cannot be excluded.

Fig. 3. PG0947+396. The linear size is < 4.28 kpc. The SED is flat at GHz frequencies but it can be considered steep at all frequencies within uncertainties. The MHz-frequency slope may be not realistic due to technical difficulties in excluding the spiral galaxy south west of the target. A UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is consistent with the IR deduced one within 2σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. Estimates done with the wind model as in ? support the wind scenario. This object is particularly ambiguous, however the most constraining results favour either the wind scenario (if the SED is considered steep) or the corona one (if the SED is considered flat at GHz frequencies).

Fig. 4. PG0953+414. The linear size is < 3.85 kpc. The SED is flat at GHz frequencies but steeper at MHz ones. No UFO detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is consistent with the IR deduced one within 1σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The radio emission is most likely the result of a superposition of processes and it is difficult to disentangle the dominant one. The GHz spectral index is flat but not as flat as we expect for a corona dominated emission, therefore an unresolved compact jet may explain the the SED curvature.

Fig. 5. PG1352+183. The linear size is < 2.44 kpc. The SED is flat at GHz frequencies (can be also inverted). No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is consistent with the IR deduced one within 1σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. According to the SED shape, the radio emission could be fully explained with coronal emission, however an unresolved jet cannot be ruled-out.

Fig. 6. 2MASXJ1402+26. The linear size is $< 4.42 \text{ kpc}$. The SED is flat then steep, with an optically thin component becoming dominant at GHz frequencies. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is compatible with the IR deduced one within 1σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The spectral shape suggests radio emission at GHz frequencies could be fully explained with SF, but the flattening toward lower ones suggests some self-absorption may be present.

Fig. 7. PG1402+261. The linear size is $< 7.25 \text{ kpc}$. The SED is flat then steep, with an optically thin component becoming dominant at GHz frequencies. Variability is suggested by the location of FIRST and VLASS flux density. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is compatible with the IR deduced one within 1σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. Radio emission could be fully explained with SF at higher frequencies, but the joint presence of variability and the break in the spectrum may point to a different scenario, as a jet base.

Fig. 8. PG1416-129. The linear size is $< 2 \text{ kpc}$. The SED is flat at GHz frequencies and shows signs of variability. No UFO detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is a factor 34 higher than the IR deduced one (out of the 3σ uncertainty). The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The SED is not flat enough to be dominated by the corona, therefore an unresolved jet cannot be ruled-out. However ?, with EVN observations, detect a compact core (linear size $< 10 \text{ pc}$). The authors also report (from ?) a C-band flux density a factor ~ 0.42 smaller than the one presented in this work, then attribute the dominant radio origin to the corona. We can infer our observations collect the superposition of more extended emission to the one of a pure compact corona.

Fig. 9. PG1427+480. The linear size is $< 3.02 \text{ kpc}$. The SED is flat. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is compatible with the IR deduced one within 1σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The MHz detection of a faint feature on the north-east side of the core deserves further investigations. Maybe a young jet could be the responsible for the SED shape, while the extended feature belongs to an older episode.

Fig. 10. PG1435-067. The linear size is $< 2.83 \text{ kpc}$. The SED is flat at GHz frequencies. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is compatible with the IR deduced one within 1σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. While the SED is not flat enough to favour the corona as main source of radio emission, the spectrum could be dominated by an unresolved jet.

Fig. 11. SDSSJ1444+06. The linear size is $< 2.96 \text{ kpc}$. The SED is flat in both regimes. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is compatible with the IR deduced one within 3σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The spectral slope is too steep for the radio emission to be dominated by the corona. An unresolved jet is the most likely the dominant radio origin.

Fig. 12. PG1626+554. The linear size is < 2.09 kpc. The SED is steep then flat, with an optically thick component becoming dominant at GHz frequencies. The steep MHz-frequency spectrum may be due to some negative flux density contours at 1.5 GHz. No UFO detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is compatible with the IR deduced one within 3σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The SED is too steep to be dominated by coronal emission. Single mechanism at the origin of radio is difficult to constrain, however an unresolved jet may explain the SED curvature.

Fig. 13. PG0052+251. The linear size is 11.4 kpc. The SED is steep at all frequencies within uncertainties. No UFO detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is compatible with the IR deduced one within 2σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The north-south extension, together with the steep SED shape, suggests a symmetric outflow, either in the form of a wind or a jet. However ? report (VLA in A configuration) a C-band flux density a factor ~ 0.57 smaller than the one presented in this work. The authors also detect a VLBA compact core, then attribute the dominant radio origin to the corona. We can infer our observations collect the superposition of extended emission to the one of a compact corona.

Fig. 14. 2MASXJ1051+35. The linear size is 8.7 kpc. The SED is flat then steep, with an optically thin component becoming dominant at GHz frequencies. A UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is a factor 32 higher than the IR deduced one. The target exceeds the 3σ uncertainty region around the Güdel–Benz relation. Estimates done with the wind model as in ? favour the wind scenario, indeed the extension, together with the synchrotron break, suggests either a wind or a compact jet.

Fig. 15. PG1114+445. The linear size is 22.35 kpc. The SED is steep dominated by an optically thin component. The UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission consistent with the IR deduced one within 3σ . The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ . Estimates done with the wind model as in ? favour the wind scenario. The extended shape and the UFO detection suggest radio emission could be related to a wind or a jet.

Fig. 16. PG1202+281. The linear size is 8.7 kpc. The integrated SED is steep dominated by an optically thin component. A UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is consistent with the IR deduced one within $1/2\sigma$. The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within $1/2\sigma$ uncertainty. Estimates done with the wind model as in ? favour the wind scenario. The bulk of radio emission is probably related to the presence of outflows, even if it remains difficult to distinguish between AGN driven winds and a low-power jet.

Fig. 17. PG1307+085. The linear size is 35 kpc. The SED is steep within the uncertainties. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is consistent with the IR deduced one within 2σ . The offset of FIRST flux density of a factor 0.37 with respect to the proprietary data suggests variability. The target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. The extension together with the hints of variability suggest contribution from a jet.

Fig. 18. LBQS1338-0038. The linear size is 26.1 kpc. The SED is steep, dominated by an optically thin extended component. The UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is consistent with the IR deduced one within 3σ . The offset of RACS, and VLASS flux densities with respect to the computed slope suggests some variability. The target exceeds the 3σ uncertainty region around the Güdel–Benz relation. Estimates done with the wind model as in ? favour the wind scenario, therefore the radio emission may be dominated by wind shocks, but a jet scenario cannot be ruled-out.

Fig. 19. HB891529+050. The linear size is 14.35 kpc. The SED is steep dominated by an optically thin component. The offset of VLASS flux density with respect to the predicted slope may be hint of variability, even though all the other points are consistent with expectations. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is a factor 9 higher than the IR deduced one. The target does exceeds the 3σ uncertainty region around the Güdel–Benz relation. The extension suggests the presence of an outflow, maybe an unresolved jet.

Fig. 20. PG0804+761. The linear size is 41.8 kpc. The SED is steep, dominated by an optically thin extended component. The B,C extranuclear component have a steep spectrum, compatible with shock driven radio emission. The UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission, for the nuclear component (A), is a factor 25 higher than the IR deduced one. The core of the target follows the Güdel–Benz relation within 1σ uncertainty. Estimates done with the wind model as in ? favour the wind scenario. Very similar to the already studied 2MASXJ1653+23. The radio emission is probably dominated by shocks from winds or jets.

Fig. 21. PG1425+267. The linear size is 1.2 Mpc. The SED is steep dominated by an optically thin component. The core SED is flat, as expected from a jet base. No UFO is detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is a factor 76 higher than the IR deduced one. The core of the target exceeds the 3σ uncertainty region around the Güdel–Benz. The radio emission is unambiguously related to the presence of a relativistic jet.

Fig. 22. 2MASXJ1653+23. The linear size is 45.6 kpc. The integrated SED is steep dominated by an optically thin component, but the core one shows a break. The B,C extranuclear component have a steep spectrum, compatible with shock driven radio emission. UFO detected. The SFR predicted with radio emission is comparable to the IR deduced one within 1σ . The core of the target exceeds the 3σ uncertainty region around the Güdel–Benz relation. Estimates done with the wind model as in ? favour the wind scenario. The bulk of radio emission is unambiguously related to the presence of outflows, even if it remains difficult to distinguish between AGN driven winds and a low-power jet.